

Bamsurgeon (ctDNA, remove duplicates then simulate)

- Batch
- A 1
 - B 2
 - C 3
 - D 4
 - E 5
 - F 6
 - G 7
 - H 8
 - I 9
 - J 10
 - K 11
 - L 12

- Allele fraction type
- Reference truth
 - Real variant
 - Simulated variant

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